

THE INVESTIGATION OF SELF-DEVELOPMENT IS A TYPE OF PERSONAL ACTIVITY

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ABSTRACT

This article describes the notion of self-development as a type of personality activity of a subject-subject nature its types and stages .

Key words: personality activity, self-directed, value-oriented activit, intellectual, socio-cultural and professional activities.

Self-development is a type of personality activity of a subject-subject nature, aimed at a positive change in personal and professional qualities on the basis of self-knowledge, self-determination, self-government, self-improvement and creative self-realization [1]. Youthful self-development, according to L.N.Kulikova, is a process of independent, holistic, self-directed, value-oriented activity of an individual in continuous self-change as an enrichment of moral experience and spiritual and moral forces in accordance with the inner image of the “I” and actual social expectations [2, p. 59]. The stages of self-development include: *preparation, awareness, reassessment, actions* [9, p. 173–174]. The difference between the categories of “development” and “self-development” lies in the fact that during the development of a personality, evolutionary movement, growth is perceived as a kind of change, stimulated, initiated from the outside, and in self-development this process comes from the personality itself [1,p.73]. Personal development differs significantly from its self-development. If the first process is non-subjective, then in the second it is the personality that acts as a subject, an active creator of himself. The processes of development and self-development of the personality are effective in all age periods of a person’s life, if the optimality of their ratio is ensured [3, p. 92]. An analysis of the literature made it possible to identify three types of self-development of a university student: *intellectual, socio-cultural and professional*.

Picture -1. Self Development -conscious pursuit of personal growth and process.

Intellectual self-development. In the psychological and pedagogical literature, there is still no clear definition of the concept of “intellectual self-development”. There is the term “intellectual self-regulation”, introduced into science by M.A. Kholodnaya [5], considered as the ability to arbitrarily manage one’s own intellectual activity, independently monitor the strengths and weaknesses in the work of one’s intellect, and, most importantly, purposefully build a self-learning process. The term “intellectual self-development” was introduced into the educational process of a secondary school by V.I. Zemtsova. Intellectual self-development is a purposeful and conscious process of developing skills by a student, namely: making logical conclusions, operating with ABSTRACT concepts, performing analysis and synthesis operations, structuring incoming information, understanding the specifics of mental operations in the process of educational activity based on internally significant aspirations and external influences (interactions with the teacher and other students). The criteria and indicators of the process of intellectual self-development of students are: *motivational-value* (reflects the characteristics of changes in the motivational sphere of students; its implementation is aimed at developing in schoolchildren the desire for intellectual self-development and the acceptance of intellectual self-development as a value); *cognitive* (characterized by a change in knowledge of the content of intellectual self-development, mastery of techniques and ways of self-expanding the limits of one’s own knowledge and skills); *activity* (includes the ability of students to work with concepts, judgments, conclusions, evaluate the skills of others, independently acquire the necessary knowledge) [7; 9]. The intellectual self-development of a student is based on resolving the contradiction between the real qualities of the individual and the ideal image of an intellectually developed subject, presented from the outside or created independently¹ [7; 9]. Intellectual self-development¹ is a stable integrative quality of a

¹ Левина, О. Н. Организационно-педагогические условия интеллектуального саморазвития подростка: автореф. дис.... канд. пед. наук: 13.00.01. — Оренбург, 2013.

personality, expressed in the subject's desire for self-knowledge, intellectual self-improvement, self-organization of thinking as a systemic, integrative, logical, conceptual one [7, p. 13]. Self-development of the intellectual sphere is the activity and development of the individual through progressive self-movement in social relations aimed at the area of the psyche, characterized by types of thinking, thinking style, mental operations, cognitive skills, an integral system of general educational and special knowledge [10, With. 10].

Sociocultural self-development. An analysis of the literature makes it possible to define the socio-cultural self-development of a university student as follows: the student's development of himself as a subject of social relations, a subject of communication, interpersonal communication, a participant in public life, a performer of various social roles, a consumer of cultural achievements, a bearer of social and cultural values; the development of "the ability to live a stable life for the benefit of oneself and society" (L.P. Lazareva); development of social responsibility and self-control, the ability to rationally organize leisure; development: skills of life in modern society and citizenship, organizational skills, skills in oral and written communication, interpersonal communication skills, group work skills, skills in performing various social roles in a team, readiness for family life [4, p. 15–16]. "The more achievements of universal human experience, culture, are manifested and used at a higher level in a specific activity, the more this activity is cultural, the greater the level of socialization is the subject" [8, p. 43]. "To socialize an individual is not to fit him into the crowd, not to liken him to others, and not even to ensure his "rough adjustment" to meet the requirements of society, but to give his life activity the most human character, the most different from the biological, the most loaded with culture" [8]. Professional self-development is the process of integrating external professional training and internal movement, the personal development of a person. External professional training sets the content, forms, schemes of professional reflection, and internal movement provides energy, the realization of the personal meaning of professional self-development. External training and internal movement are the constituent processes of professional self-development. It consists of two components: external conditions (which are created by certain positions) and internal abilities (they are mastered by the subject himself), which suggest the presence of: a) needs - the need for renewal, development, self-knowledge, understanding of one's actions; b) goals; c) funds [11.,p.116]. One of the conditions for successful self-development of a university student is goal-setting. Features of goal-setting in the field of self-development are disclosed by the author in another article.

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